

ONLINE GAMING: HEALTH RELATED EFFECTS AMONG STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study delves into the health-related implications of online gaming among students at Holy Name University. Through surveys and focus group discussions, the research examines demographic characteristics, gaming patterns, perceived effects on physical, mental, and emotional well-being, as well as the correlation between gaming duration and health perceptions. The data revealed that a significant portion of respondents are male, predominantly around the age of 20, with diverse gaming habits. Most students reported spending 2-3 hours per day playing online games, primarily on cellphones using mobile data. Action and adventure games are the preferred genres. While online gaming was found to have negative effects such as poor nutrition, lack of concentration, and mood swings, it was also perceived as a stress-relieving activity. The study recommends tailored health education initiatives, counseling programs, and monitoring of internet usage to mitigate potential negative impacts. Furthermore, addressing communication technology issues is advised to foster responsible internet use among students. Despite the identified drawbacks, online gaming was acknowledged as a source of stress relief and motivation for students. These findings highlight the importance of promoting balanced internet usage and implementing strategies to support students in managing their online gaming habits effectively.

Keywords: *Demographic Profiles, Health-Related Effects, Online Gaming, Technological Addiction*

INTRODUCTION

There are plenty of changes in our daily life with the rise of internet, in particular the rise also allows online games to bloom. In today's society, people and internet are indivisible, students are also dependent in the internet for its educational and entertainment purposes (Parel, 2017). Online gaming is quite popular nowadays as a sort of entertainment for the society that targets people of all ages: young and adult (Zamani, Chashmi, & Hedayati, 2009). It is one of many people's popular recreational activities, and young people who play online games said that they're playing just for fun.

Playing is an innate part of the human experience and it is also a habitual leisure-time activity for many gamers (Hu, Stavropoulos, Anderson, Scerri & Collard, 2018). It is very captivating with all the new and improved technology created through the years. In online gaming, there are lots of categories and there are different trivial level of the game and adventures that makes the gamers of all ages excited and as the game engross to different higher level, the challenging obstacles of the games makes the gamers crave more and if they lose they keep on playing until they win to recover from the loss. In the current digital era, the play has expanded because of the acceleration and ballooning of videogames with an exceeding 135 billion dollars estimated global market value (Wijman, 2018).

For most people, online gaming is one of the best time they have ever acquired, especially for teenagers, young people and students. Students who play online games are just having fun. They're not just playing because of some sort of seriousness, but also because they just want to feel relief. Students tend to feel stressed during school hours due to loads of school work and relieve their stress through playing it. For some, it is said that playing online games has a number of reasons to be played, for it can be a stress reliever, challenge and competition, relaxation, enjoyment, social interaction, and even mentally escaping from the real world (Griffiths, 2015).

There are relative number of studies, all of which suggest that excessive online gaming also have a wide range of negative psychosocial consequences for a minority of people affected. In some cases, these can include education, hobbies, socializing, time with family, and sleep; increased stress; an absence of real-life relationships; lower psychosocial well-being and loneliness; decreased academic achievement; increased inattention; aggressive/oppositional behavior and hostility; maladaptive coping; decreases in verbal memory performance; maladaptive cognitions; and suicidal ideation. According to Griffiths et al. (2012), many health and medical consequences results from excessive gaming (both online and offline) in addition to the reported negative psychosocial consequences. These included epileptic seizures, auditory hallucinations, obesity, wrist pain, neck pain, blisters, calluses, sore tendons, and numbness of fingers, sleep abnormalities, and repetitive strain injuries (Griffiths, 2015).

An experience that relates to this study is about a student who plays online games to relieve stress but ends up being stress because if he doesn't play often, his ranking to the game will suddenly drop. In addition to this, he also shares that he experiences sleepless nights, feels pain in the eye, and sometimes he skips his meal. Another

experience is that some students shares that they feel neck pain and dizziness after playing. Somehow, the researcher also observed students playing online games while I have my class discussion, the result would be a lesser concentration in class discussion for they are craving to play. An article also mentions about dangerous online games that targets children and adolescents that presents various 'dares' and if they fail, they are goaded to take their own life. Some anonymous person will instruct the gamers to engage in odd activities such as waking up at night or overcoming a fear. The gamers are then told to video and film themselves doing these activities, and if they succeed, the anonymous person will encourage them to partake in more dangerous dares that involves self-harm and eventually leading to suicide. These experiences demonstrate how online games brought changes to students in regards to physical, mental and emotional health.

Other studies (Griffiths, 2015) focus on the general consequences of online gaming addiction. Other studies (Zamani, Chashmi, & Hedayati, 2009) specified their scope on computer games rather than online games. Given the limitations of the studies mentioned, the purpose of this research is to determine if there is a significant relationship between the amount of time spent on playing online games and the health-related effects on the respondents.

Research Questions

The purpose of the study was to determine the health-related effects in relation to online gaming among the students at Holy Name University. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following sub-questions:

1. What is demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender; and
 - 1.3 Course?
2. What is the method utilized by the respondents in playing online games in terms of:
 - 2.1 Gadget used;
 - 2.2 Type of connection used; and
 - 2.3 Type of online games?
3. What is the respondents' online gaming frequency in terms of:
 - 3.1 Number of hours per day; and
 - 3.2 Time of playing?
4. What are the health-related effects on Online Game in terms of:
 - 5.1 Physical;
 - 5.2 Mental; and
 - 5.3 Emotional?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the amount of time spent on playing online games and the perception of the gamers of the health-related effects of online gaming?
6. What recommendations can be formulated based on the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher employed a quantitative-qualitative research approach. A descriptive design was employed, where the respondents were interviewed using a self-made questionnaire as a research tool to gather data for the study. Additionally, a focus group discussion was conducted to elicit responses to specific questions, facilitated by the researcher, serving as the basis for the qualitative aspect of the research.

Research Environment

This study was conducted at Holy Name University, located in Tagbilaran City, Bohol, during the school year 2019-2020. College students participated in providing information relevant to the study. Holy Name University is a Philippine Accrediting Association of Schools, Colleges, and Universities (PAASCU) accredited institution renowned for providing high-quality education and training. The aim of this research output was to contribute the study's findings for the benefit of the school and its students.

Research Respondents

The chosen respondents are college students in all levels of Holy Name University. There were 117 college students who were chosen through a snowball sampling in the quantitative method.

Protecting the autonomy and dignity of the respondents, the researcher only distributed the questionnaire to the respondents after thoroughly explaining to them the aim, motivation, purpose, research questions, and other necessary information that enable the respondents to make the decision whether they prefer to join or not.

After the informed consent was given to the respondents, they were asked to answer the questionnaire.

No identifying markers on the answered questionnaire were upheld during the entire duration of the research. In cases wherein the questionnaire induced some negative emotions or memories, the researchers assisted them in securing the help the respondents needed.

Criteria in selecting the respondents in the quantitative method:

The criteria for selecting respondents in the quantitative method encompassed several key factors. Firstly, participants were required to have engaged in online gaming activities on a regular basis, specifically playing games on 5 to 7 days per week. Secondly, individuals who played multiple games were sought after, reflecting a diverse gaming experience. Lastly, respondents were expected to have dedicated a significant amount of time to online gaming, spending a minimum of 2 to 3 hours per day immersed in gaming

activities. These criteria were carefully chosen to target a sample group that represented active and committed online gamers, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of their gaming behaviors and habits within the context of the study.

The respondents of the qualitative method were chosen based on the result of the quantitative method. There were 8 respondents that were chosen based on the amount of time they play online games.

Criteria in selecting the respondents in the qualitative method:

Criteria for selecting respondents in the qualitative method emphasized individuals who spent 8 hours or more per day engaging in online gaming activities. This criterion was strategically chosen to target participants who exhibited a high level of involvement and immersion in online gaming, potentially providing deeper insights into their experiences, behaviors, and perceptions related to prolonged gaming sessions. By focusing on this specific subset of respondents, the qualitative aspect of the research aimed to explore in-depth the nuances and implications of extensive online gaming habits on various aspects of the participants' lives, including their physical and mental well-being, social interactions, and overall lifestyle. Through the qualitative interviews and discussions with these selected respondents, the research sought to uncover detailed narratives, perspectives, and experiences that could enrich the understanding of the complexities surrounding prolonged online gaming and its impact on individuals within the college student population at Holy Name University.

Research Instruments

The instrument used in the study is a self-made questionnaire. It is made up of questions which can be answered by checking the space of the chosen answer. The questionnaire is about online gaming assessment, and it contains profiling questions, the amount of time spent on playing online games in a day, the number of online games played, the time of the day the gamers normally play, and the effects of playing online games as a health risk to physical, mental and emotional health.

The questionnaire on Online Gaming: Health Related Effects Among Students, a quantitative and qualitative study had two (2) parts. The demographic profile of the respondents was the first part which included the respondent's age, gender, course as well as the method in playing online games and the frequency of playing online games by the respondents which can be answered in a yes or no.

The second part covered the respondents' health related effects of online gaming and is divided three subparts. The first subpart was the physical health related effects. This part covered the respondent's physical symptoms in playing the online games.

The second subpart was the mental health related effects experience by the respondents. Lastly, the third subpart inquired about the emotional health related effects of the respondents in playing online games.

The Likert scale was used to determine the respondents' health related effects frequency with the statement: 1.00 - 1.80 = Never; 1.81 - 2.60 = Rarely, 2.61 - 3.40 = Sometimes; 3.41 - 4.20 = Often times; 4.21 - 5.00 = Always.

The questionnaire for Online Games; Health Related Effects Among Students was validated through pilot-testing on 30 respondents. The respondents subjected for pilot-testing were not research respondents nor studying in the research locale. The result was then validated by a statistician as to the questionnaire's reliability using Chi-square test of independence with a level of significance of 0.05

Research Procedure

Gathering of Data. Modifications were made when necessary. The researcher has submitted the study protocol to HNU-Ethics Review Board to secure the ethical clearance for the study. Only after receiving the ethical clearance, gathering of data begun. After confirming the validity and reliability of the questionnaire, it was pilot tested to respondents. The respondents were asked to fill-up the questionnaire during their free time and in the location that they feel comfortable and safe. To be able to gather data and information, a letter was made by the researcher, and was sent to the Dean of the different colleges of Holy Name University asking permission to conduct the study to the college students. After the official permission was granted by the dean, the questionnaires were given to the respondents. As the respondents answer the questionnaires, it was collected and consolidated to be submitted to the statistical adviser of the study for the statistical treatment.

A focal group discussion was also conducted to elicit responses from the excessive online gamers. There were 8 respondents who undergone such discussions which was facilitated by the researchers on a specific time. This would be the basis of the qualitative type of research on the study.

Treatment of Data. The research questionnaires were collected, and the data was tallied, collated, and subjected to treatment and interpretation. Tabulation was made to show the relationships which was seen among the data. After doing the process, it was interpreted by the researchers:

1. Chi- Square Test of Independence (used to determine significance of relationship between two nominal variables)

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(f_o - f_e)^2}{f_e}$$

*where : f_o = observed frequency
 f_e = expected frequency*

2. Mean

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i}{n}$$

Where: x=scores

N = sample size

3. Percentage

$$Percentage(\%) = \frac{f}{N} \times 100$$

where: f = frequency

N = sample size

RESULTS

Table 1
Age Profile of the Respondents

Age Bracket	Frequency	Percent
18-21	90	76.9
22-26	26	22.2
27 and above	1	0.9

Figure 1
Age Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 shows the respondent's age bracket on the number of online gamers based on the given age. Majority of the respondents who plays online games are from aged 20 with a total of 34 respondents out of the 117 online gamers which has a total percentage of 29.1% while the least number of respondents comes from the age of 27 or only at 0.9%.

The study of Gough (2019) relates to the table of the age profile of the respondents wherein the majority of the online gamers comes from the 18 to 35 age demographic with a percentage of 40%, followed by gamers under 18 years old with a percentage of 21%, the same with gamers with the aged of 50 and above with a percentage of 21%, while the least number comes from aged 36 to 49 years old with a percentage of 18%.

Table 2
Gender Profile of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	83	70.9
Female	34	29.1
Total	117	100

Figure 2
Gender Profile of the Respondents

Table 2 presented the gender profile of the respondents. The male dominated the total number of gamers with a total of 83 respondents (70.9%) compared to the female respondents which comprises only a total of 34 out of the 117 respondents with a percentage of 29.1%. According to the Entertainment Software Association (ESA) with their updated survey this 2019, the male dominated the population of online gamers with a total percentage of 54%, compared to females which is closer to become equal with the males having a percentage of 46%.

Among the gaming population, teenage and adult males display much more addictive use of internet gaming in terms of screen hours, addiction, and negative health effects, which also caused death in isolated incidents. Adult males appeared to spend more time playing, playing 4.68 hours a day and 27.76 hours a week on average (Kirby et al., 2014). Overall, males devoted more time and energy to betting on computers than females, indicating that computers are male toys (Kuss, 2013; Vollmer et al., 2014). It is important to note that males design the majority of games on the market for males (Spekman et al., 2013). In reality, gaming firms target male customers and capitalize on this strategy to boost sales (Kuss, 2013; Vollmer et al., 2014). This may explain in part the increased use of gaming in males and the increased susceptibility of men to Internet Gaming Disorder (Chen, 2018).

Table 3
Course Profile of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percent
CHS:		
BSN (Bachelor of science in Nursing)	27	23.1
BSMT (Bachelor of Science in Medical Technology)	1	.9
CBA:		
BSA (Bachelor of Science in Accountancy)	13	11.1
BSBA-MA (Bachelor of Science in Business Administration – Major in Management Accounting)	8	6.8
BSBA-FM (Bachelor of Science in Business Administration – Major in Financial Management)	12	10.3
BSHRM (Bachelor of Science in Hotel and Restaurant Management)	15	12.8
BSTM (Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management)	4	3.4
COECS:		
BSECE (Bachelor of Science in Electronics and Communications Engineering)	4	3.4
BSCE (Bachelor of Science in Civil Engineering)	18	15.4
BSCS (Bachelor of Science in Computer Studies)	1	.9
BSIT (Bachelor of Science in Information Technology)	5	4.3
CAS:		
BSPSYCH (Bachelor of Science in Psychology)	1	.9
BSCRIM (Bachelor of Science in Criminology)	8	6.8
Total	117	100.0

Figure 3

Course Profile of the Respondents

Table 3 shows the course profile of the respondents. The highest number of respondents are from the Bachelor of Science in Nursing with a total number of 27 respondents with a percentage of 23.1%. While the least number of online games are from the Bachelor of Science in Psychology, Bachelor of Science in Computer Studies and from the Bachelor of Science in Medical Technology which has only 1 respondent each with a percentage of 0.9%.

Table 4
Gadget used for Online Gaming

	N	Percent	Percent of Cases
Cellphone	108	76.1	92.3
Laptop	16	11.3	13.7
PC	14	9.9	12.0
Tab/iPad	4	2.8	3.4
Total	142	100.0	121.4

Table 4 illustrates the gadgets used for online gaming. Majority of the respondents used cellphones for online gaming with a frequency of 108 out of the total 117 respondents with a percentage of 76.1 %. While the least utilized gadget for online gaming is tab/iPad which has a frequency of 4 with a percentage of 2.8 %. According to a survey, even though there are variety of gadgets used in playing online games, mobile phones remain the most popular device used in playing online games. This is in line with the findings of 2018, where mobile phones were also the most commonly used gaming device (Harris, 2019). At the same time, the share of mobile phone users who say a desktop, laptop or tablet, computer is their primary device for going online has fallen from 53% in 2013 to 30% in 2019 (Anderson, 2019).

Table 5
Type of Connection Used in Online Gaming

	N	Percent	Percent of Cases
Home	68	29.2	58.6
Mobile Data	90	38.6	77.6
Internet Café	24	10.3	20.7
School's Free Wifi	51	21.9	44.0
Total	233	100.0	200.9

On table 5, it reflected the type of connection used in online gaming. Mobile data has the highest frequency on the type of connection used in online gaming with a total of 90 and with a percentage of 38.6 %. Further, internet cafes is the least type of connection with a total of 24 and with a percentage of 10.3 %. According to a survey, fully 58% of 18- to 29-year-olds say they mostly go online through a smartphone or mobile data, up from 41% in 2013. Still, this growth is evident across all age groups. Among non-broadband

users, 45% say they do not have broadband at home because their smartphone lets them do everything they need to do online, up from 27% in 2015. At the same time, the share of non-broadband users who say their smartphone is the most important reason for not having a high-speed internet connection where they live has nearly doubled over the same time period (from 12% to 23%). And while affordability remains a commonly cited barrier, the share of non-broadband adopters who say the cost of a monthly subscription is the most important reason for not having these services has fallen from 33% in 2015 to 21% today (Anderson, 2019).

Table 6
Type of Online Games Utilized by the Respondents

Online Games	Frequency	Percent	Percent of Cases
Action and Adventure Games	97	13.3	82.9
Casino Games	30	4.1	25.6
Educational Games	58	7.9	49.6
Puzzle Games	61	8.3	52.1
Board Games	40	5.5	34.2
Massively Multiplayer Online Games	82	11.2	70.1
Strategy Games	92	12.6	78.6
Sport Games	68	9.3	58.1
Shooting Games	68	9.3	58.1
Racing Games	71	9.7	60.7
Role Playing Games	57	7.8	48.7
MOB games	7	1.0	6.0
Simulation Games	1	0.1	0.9
Total	732	100.0	625.6

Figure 4. Type of Online Games Utilized by the Respondent

Table 6 presented the type of online games played by the respondents. The highest number of respondents played action and adventure games which has total

frequency of 97 and a total percentage of cases of 82.9 %. It is roughly followed by strategy games with a total number of 92 and a percentage of cases of 78.6 %. The third most common online game used by the respondents is the massively multiplayer online games with a total number of 82 or with a percentage of cases of 70.1 %. While the least online game played by the respondents is the simulation games which comprises of only 1 and with a percentage of case of 0.9 %. According to a study, the most played game genre is Action Games with a percentage of 26.9%, followed by Shooting Games with a percentage of 20.9%, third is Role Playing Games with a percentage of 11.3%, fourth is Sport Games with a percentage of 11.1%, fifth is Adventure Games with a percentage of 7.9%, followed by Fighting Games with a percentage of 7.8% (Gough, 2019).

Table 7
Number of Hours Playing Online Games Per Day

	Frequency	Percent
2-3 HOURS	53	45.3
4-5 HOURS	39	33.3
6-7 HOURS	14	12.0
8 HOURS AND ABOVE	11	9.4
Total	117	100.0

Figure 5. Number of Hours Playing Online Games Per Day

The number of hours spent playing online games per day is presented on this table. It shows that majority of the respondents spent 2 – 3 hour per day in playing with a total of 53 respondents out of the total 117 and with a percentage of 45.3 %. While the 8

hours and above bracket has the least number of frequency with a total of 11 and with a percentage of 9.4 %.

Table 8
Time of Playing Online Games

	N	Percent	Percent of Cases
MORNING	36	13.6	31.0
AFTERNOON	52	19.7	44.8
NIGHT	98	37.1	84.5
MIDNIGHT	44	16.7	37.9
DAWN	34	12.9	29.3
Total	264	100.0	227.6

Table 8 presented the time of playing online games among the respondents. Most of the online gamers plays during the night with a total of 98 and with a percentage of cases of 84.5 %. It further showed that during the dawn is the least time of the day that is spent in online gaming with only a total of 34 and with a percentage of cases of 29.3 %.

According to an article, online gamers who play at night often get less sleep than they need because they delay their bedtimes to keep playing. In a survey of close to 1,000 regular gamers who were age 13 and older (mean 28.7 years), two-thirds said they frequently lost sleep because they were playing video games. Other data suggest that almost three out of four Americans play video games, and nine out of 10 do not sleep as much as recommended (Boyles, 2016). In table 8, most of the respondents answered that they often play online games during at night, which may alter their sleep.

Table 9
Physical Health Related Effects of Online Gaming

Physical Effects	Descriptive Rating Scale					Average
	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always	
1. Fatigue	35 (29.9%)	36 (30.8%)	36 (30.8%)	7 (6.0%)	3 (2.6%)	Rarely
2. Poor Posture	23 (19.7%)	36 (30.8%)	42 (35.9%)	13 (11.1)	3 (2.6)	Sometimes
3. Poor Nutrition	37 (31.6%)	45 (38.5%)	28 (23.9%)	6 (5.1%)	1 (0.9%)	Rarely
4. Back Pain	21 (17.9%)	33 (28.2 %)	35 (29.9%)	22 (18.8%)	6 (5.1%)	Sometimes
5. Neck aches	17 (14.5%)	39 (33.3%)	34 (29.1 %)	19 (16.2%)	8 (6.8%)	Rarely
6. Shoulder Pain	19 (16.2%)	38 (32.5%)	37 (31.6%)	18 (15.4%)	5 (4.3%)	Rarely

7. Hand Cramps	30 (25.6%)	31 (26.5%)	36 (30.8%)	12 (10.3%)	8 (6.8%)	Sometimes
8. Eye Pain	11 (9.4%)	27 (23.1%)	36 (30.8%)	28 (23.9%)	15 (12.8%)	Sometimes
9. Tearing of Eyes	21 (17.9%)	24 (20.5%)	33 (28.2%)	25 (21.4%)	14 (12.0%)	Sometimes
10. Headache	17 (14.5%)	36 (30.8%)	34 (29.1%)	21 (17.9%)	9 (7.7%)	Rarely
11. Dizziness	32 (27.4%)	40 (34.2%)	32 (27.4%)	9 (7.7%)	4 (3.4%)	Rarely
12. Tardiness	21 (17.9%)	41 (35.0%)	34 (29.1%)	13 (11.1%)	8 (6.8%)	Rarely
General Average						Rarely

On this table, the highest frequency of the respondents experiences poor nutrition as the most common physical effects of online gaming with a frequency of 45 respondents or a total percentage of 38.5 % and with a qualitative description of Rarely. On the other hand, the least physical effects of online gaming is tearing of eyes which has a frequency of 33 and with a total percentage of 28.2% with a qualitative description of sometimes.

In a study measuring the effects of digital gaming on nutrition habits in university students, it was found that as the duration of playing digital games increases, negative eating habits increases, minds constantly occupied and primary needs such as nutrition lost importance. They also observed that main meals are skipped and snacking was preferred. In another study conducted on students, Smahel et al (2012) stated that as the duration of playing internet games increased, nutrition habits deteriorated and children became depressed. Similarly, it is reported that children with internet addiction encountered problems including nutrition disorders (Tetik et.al, 2018).

Table 10
Mental Health Related Effects of Online Gaming

Mental Effects	Descriptive Rating					
	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always	Average
1. Poor Concentration	29 (24.8%)	41 (35.0%)	32 (27.4%)	13 (11.1%)	2 (1.7%)	Rarely
2. Confusion	44 (37.6%)	33 (28.2%)	26 (22.2%)	13 (11.1%)	1 (0.9%)	Never
3. Obsessive (Uncontrollable thoughts)	34 (29.1%)	39 (33.3%)	28 (23.9%)	14 (12.0%)	2 (1.7%)	Rarely
4. Compulsive (Repetitive behaviors)	43 (36.8%)	30 (25.6%)	29 (24.8%)	15 (12.8%)	0 (0%)	Never

5. Impulsive	50 (42.7%)	31 (26.5%)	28 (23.9%)	8 (6.8%)	0 (0%)	Never
6. Low Self-esteem	48 (41.0%)	31 (26.5%)	21 (17.9%)	10 (8.5%)	7 (6.0%)	Never
General Average						Never

Table 10 discusses on the mental effects of gaming. It illustrates that poor concentration has the highest frequency in terms of mental effects on the respondents with a frequency of 41 and with a percentage of 35.0% with a qualitative description of rarely. Moreover, impulsiveness is the least mental effects of online gamers with a frequency of 50 and with a corresponding percentage of 42.7% with a qualitative description of Never.

According to a study, college students spending too much time on online games every week tend to suffer from worsened learning ability, concentration problems, poor academic performance, and decreased interactions with other people (Lin et al., 2013). Playing online games for a long time will create a negative impact on academic performance. Lack of concentration will be an issue in spending more time in playing online games (Ali, 2018).

According to a study in which during gaming, gamers has decrease impulsiveness. A person playing a video game with a first-person shooter like Halo or Unreal Tournament has to make quick decisions. It turns out that rapid decision-making improves the visual abilities of the player but comes at a cost, according to new research: reducing the ability of the individual to suppress impulsive behavior. This decrease in what is called "proactive executive regulation" seems to be another way to increase aggressive behavior through violent video games. The ability of people to override aggressive impulses is largely dependent on good executive control capacity, as will be presented at an annual meeting in Honolulu at the American Psychological Association (APA). So social psychologists are looking at how this skill is impacted by a variety of factors, including media exposure, frustration, so alcohol. Two forms of mechanisms of cognitive control play a major role: constructive and reactive. Researchers have found that playing action video games is correlated with increased visuospatial attention capacity, but also decreased constructive cognitive function. According to Anderson, their studies are the first to connect violent video game play within the same study with both beneficial and harmful effect (Anderson, 2013).

Another study talks about the impulsive behaviors of the gamers, in which impulsiveness is related to the development of addictive gaming behavior. Their findings confirm that the more impulsive young people are more likely to develop addictive gaming behavior. Their results are consistent with recent studies suggesting that the addiction to video games is an impulse control disorder (Ding et al., 2014; Gentile et al., 2011). Results of the meta-analysis carried out by MacKillop et al. (2011) of the relationship between

impulsiveness and addiction provide strong evidence that impulsiveness is related to the development of addictive behavior in general (Lloret Irlles & Morell Gomis, 2015).

Table 11
Emotional Health Related Effects on Online Gaming

Emotional Effects	Descriptive Rating					
	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always	Average
1. Depressed	63 (53.8%)	30 (25.6%)	15 (12.8%)	4 (3.4%)	5 (4.3%)	Never
2. Anxious	43 (36.8%)	44 (37.6%)	20 (17.1%)	7 (6.0%)	3 (2.6%)	Rarely
3. Irritable	27 (23.1%)	37 (31.6%)	31 (26.5%)	15 (12.8%)	7 (6.0%)	Rarely
4. Happy	2 (1.7%)	9 (7.7%)	23 (19.7%)	29 (24.8%)	54 (46.2%)	Always
5. Sad	38 (32.5%)	36 (30.8%)	32 (27.4%)	4 (3.4%)	7 (6.0%)	Never
6. Angry	23 (19.7%)	33 (28.2%)	36 (30.8%)	16 (13.7%)	9 (7.7%)	Sometimes
7. Guilt	52 (44.4%)	33 (28.2%)	21 (17.9%)	9 (7.7%)	2 (1.7%)	Never
8. Shame	57 (48.7%)	29 (24.8%)	21 (17.9%)	7 (6.0%)	3 (2.6%)	Never
General Average						Never

Table 11 discusses on the emotional effects of gaming. It shows that being happy has the highest frequency in terms of emotional effects on the respondents with a frequency of 54 and with a percentage of 46.2%. Moreover, being depressed is the least emotional effects of online gamers with a frequency of 63 and with a corresponding percentage of 53.8%.

According to a study, Improvements in mood, stress reduction, and skills and flexibility from playing video games. The study showed benefits in terms of social well-being and associated feelings for young people. Researchers found that competitive video game play for younger people was associated with increased brain activity. More specifically, using a well-validated measure of mental health and well-being, it has found evidence that playing video games with other people has had a positive effect on well-being for adult players. In a randomized controlled trial with a clinically depressed adult population, it has been shown that the beneficial effects of video games include a decrease in anxiety, frustration, depression and exhaustion and an increase in vigor. Importantly, the associated changes in brain activity and variability in heart rate supported these improvements (Johnson, 2013).

According to a study, the highest probability for depressive, musculoskeletal, and psychosomatic symptoms was found among weekday gamers, especially those who played for high Escape motives and spent an excessive amount of time gaming. Furthermore, among individuals driven by positive motives, time spent gaming was of high importance in relation to ill health, whereas among the negative motives the time spent gaming was less important (Hellstrom et al., 2015).

Table 13
Relationship Between the Amount of Time Spent and Health Related Effects of Online Gaming

Variables Correlated	Chi – Square Value	P- value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
No. of Hours Spent for Gaming and Physical Effects of Online Gaming	10.705	0.098	Accept Ho	Not Significant
No. of Hours Spent for Gaming and Mental Effects of Online Gaming	8.241	0.221	Accept Ho	Not Significant
No. of Hours Spent for Gaming and Emotional Effects of Online Gaming	4.251	0.607	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Note: Level of significance is 0.05

The relationship between the health related effects does not depend on the amount of time spent on online games. Table 13 shows the relationship between the amount of time spent on health related effects of online gaming. The P-value of 0.098, 0.221 and 0.607 indicates that the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis since the P-value is greater than 0.05 alpha level which implies no significant relationship between variables related. This implies that the physical, mental and emotional effects of online gaming are not dependent on the number of hours spent for gaming. The rejection of the null hypothesis further implies that these findings is only true to our sample but not true to the population of online gamers.

Thematic Analysis of the Qualitative Data

The researchers conducted an interview. This is to further determine experiences of the chosen respondents in relation to online gaming. The experiences may vary from one user to another.

Here are the following themes together with the supporting answers/statements of the interviewees:

Theme No. 1: Factors resulting to the inclination of online games

According to the interviewees, there are factors that entice the participants to engage in online gaming. One interviewee said,

“Family bonding, bonding na namo sa akong mga igsoon, stress reliever pud”

Another interviewee said,

“Lami sya sa feeling, basta nindot sya sa feeling kay murag maayo ka anang butanga, kay wa man mi ni excel sa sports, murag ana nalang namo gibawi”

Two of the interviewees said,

“Sress reliever”

Another one also said,

“Boredom lang gyud akoo”

One of the interviewees also stated,

“Kill the time”

Another also stated,

“Yes, stress gikan sa duty, sa skwelahan, exam nya nahagbong murag mao bitaw maka cope up nimo, malingaw ka ba, mawa sa imong huna-huna ang mga stressors nimo, nya anha ka mamalikas”.

Theme No. 2: Positive and Negative Effects of Online Gaming

As what the answers of the interviewees during the interview, there are positive and negative response with regards to online gaming in terms of physical and emotional aspect,

In regards to neglected self-care, one interviewee said,

“Labi na ug naa sa balay, dili na jud maligo”.

Another one said,

“Yes, Sometimes, samot na ug malingaw na kaayo, kanang thrilling na kaayo bitaw. Kasagaran kay kaon madugay ko ana.

One interviewee disagreed in respond to the answer stated,

“Dili pud tanan, kana rang kaon pero kanang uban dili nya exercise pud, dili man jud maka exercise ang duwa”.

With regards to the sleeping pattern, all interviewees stated that they all stayed up late to play online games, one exclaimed,

“YES, karon gani wala gani tog.”

In the time they normally play, one interviewee said,

“Kadlawn pud kay kusog internet.”

And was supported by 3 other interviewees, stated,

“kadlawn, anytime, 10pm-4am.”

“10 upwards, 10pm-5am ug walay klase kung naa dili.”

“ako kay bisan unsa man orasa bisan magklase kay magduwa man ko usahay.”

In regards to the alleviation of negative mood states and a cope to stress, one interviewee said,

“Yes, ana nalang paagi usahay aside sa mag away, mag duel nalang ug duwa.”

When they were asked if online gaming has affected their life, all responded **“neither”, they don’t know if online gaming has affected their life in a positive or negative way.**

In regards to physical, mental, and emotional problems experienced as what they perceived, one interviewee said,

“Draining kaayo sa physical, sakit sa kamot, sakit sa mata, sa emotional pud di ba mapildi ka? Masungot man jud ka. Depende ra sa duwa.”

Another two stated,

“Kung ako malingaw ra ko kay di man ko parehas sa ilaha nga ML, chill ra man akong mga duwa nya sige ra ko ug design ug balay pero kasagaran ana sakit sa mata kay nitutok baya ka sa gadget nimo.”

“Depende sa outcome sa duwa nya kung maayo imong duwa lami kaayo ang mood, pero kung dili putang ina.”

The remaining interviewees also agreed to the statement mentioned by other interviewees.

When asked why they still keep on playing despite experiencing what was mentioned as the physical and emotional problems, one of the interviewee answered,

“Lingaw, bahalag sakit ang mata lingaw man gihapon.”

Another also said,

“Lingaw, lingaw ra jud.”

Other interviewee stated,

“Huwat ra ug makabati ug grabe usa mo hunong ug duwa.”

Another also stated,

“As of now wala kay dili paman pud grabe ang nabati.”

The other interviewee talked about moderation in playing, stated,

“Ako before straight gyud ko duwa from 10 pm to 4 am or 6 am, straight gyud na walay pahuway karon kay pahuway mga duha ka oras ganahan mo duwag balik, duwag balik mo take nakog kuan para dili btaw ma strain akong mata especially karon nga nisamot ug kadaot akong mata mao nang ok kanang in moderation sa lang mabuta nako kadugayan ani.”

The other remaining interviewees also agreed that they are having fun, and they don’t care despite experiencing physical and emotional problems.

In regards to what they think about online gaming, one interviewee said,

“State of the power of reality, murag to escape from real world because life without online games people who do not have funs people will kill each other, declare wars so the chances of having world war 3 is not that high, if there is online games rather than there is xenophobia against other countries there’s somewhat unity.”

Another also stated,

“Murag addiction.”

In connection to the Health Belief Model of Rosenstock, the researchers related the respondents' answers regarding online gaming with the 4 variables; Perceived Susceptibility, Perceived Severity, Perceived Benefit, and Perceived Barriers.

In the **Perceived Susceptibility** of the respondents, they stated that online gaming is neither positively or negatively affects their life.

In the **Perceived Severity** of the respondents, they stated that they neglected self-care specifically in bathing, eating and exercise. They also stayed up late and continued to play despite experiencing eye pain and other problems stated in the quantitative questionnaire. Furthermore, they stated that online games are addictive.

In the **Perceived Benefit** of the respondents, they stated that online gaming has been a stress reliever and lessen their boredom. However, they stated that they can replace online gaming by many other things such as socialization with other people.

In the **Perceived Barriers** of the respondents, they stated that they experienced eye pain and fatigue when playing online games. Moreover, they stated that they will not change unless they experience the worst of the symptoms that they have experienced from playing online games.

Findings

Based from the data gathered, it shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:

Age. Majority of the respondents who plays online games aged 20 with a total of 34 out of 117 which has 29.1% while the least number of respondents comes from the age of 27 or only at 0.9%.

Gender. The total number of respondents from all the listed courses is 117 and 83 (70.9%) of the respondents were male students, while the 34 (29.1%) of the respondents were female students.

Course. In getting the respondents, the researchers in collaboration with the statistician agreed to gather 117 students from the total population of the college students. Majority of the respondents are from the Bachelor of Science in Nursing with a total number of 27 respondents and with a percentage of 23.1% while the least number of respondents are from the Bachelor of Science in Computer Studies and Bachelor of Science in Medical Technology which each has only 1 respondent with a percentage of 0.9%.

2. Respondents' manner of Online Gaming regarding in terms of:

Time. According to the respondents, the usual time they play online games is during night time and the least time of the day is during dawn. Also in the qualitative

research focus group discussion, the respondents normally played online games between 10pm-4am or 5am (dawn).

Duration and Frequency. According to the respondents, 2-3 hours per day spent in playing with a total of 53 respondents out of the total 117 and with a percentage of 45.3 %. While the 8 hours and above bracket has the least number of frequency with a total of 11 and with a percentage of 9.4 %.

Gadget utilized. Majority of the students used cellphones for online gaming with a 108 out of 117 respondents with a percentage of 76.1% while the least utilized is tab/iPad which has a 4 frequency with a percentage of 2.8%. Also in the qualitative research focus group discussion, the respondents answered cellphones as their gadget in online gaming.

Connection. Mobile data is the most on the type of connection used in online gaming with a total of 90 respondents with a percentage of 38.6% while internet cafés is the least type of connection with a total of 24 with a percentage of 10.3%. On the other hand, in the qualitative research focus group discussion the respondents answered that they used Wi-Fi connection when playing online gaming.

Type of Game. The respondents mostly played action and adventure games with a total of 97 out of 117 respondents with a percentage of 82.9%. It is roughly followed by strategy games with a total of 92 respondents and a percentage of cases 78.6 % and the third most common type of game played is the massively multiplayer online games with a total of number of 82 or with a percentage of cases of 70.1%. While the game that the respondent least played is the simulation game which comprises only 1 with a percentage of 0.9%. On the other hand, in the qualitative research focus group discussion the respondents answered that they usually played strategic type of games.

3. Respondents' perception on the effects in online gaming in terms of:

Physical Health. The most common physical effects that the respondents experienced is poor nutrition with 45 out of 117 respondents or a total percentage of 38.5 % with a qualitative description of rarely. While the least physical effects of online gaming the respondent experiences is tearing of eyes which has a frequency of 33 and with a total percentage of 28.2% with a qualitative description of sometimes. On the other hand, in the qualitative research focus group discussion the respondents answered that they commonly experienced eye pain.

Mental Health. Poor concentration has the highest frequency in terms of mental effects on the respondents with a frequency of 41 and with a percentage of 35.0% with a qualitative description of rarely . Moreover, impulsive is the least mental effects of online gamers with a frequency of 50 and with a corresponding percentage of 42.7 % with a qualitative description of never.

Emotional Health. Happy has the highest frequency in terms of emotional effects on the respondents with a frequency of 54 and with a percentage of 46.2% with a qualitative description of always. Moreover, being depressed is the least emotional effects of online gamers with a frequency of 63 and with a corresponding percentage of 53.8%. On the other hand, in the qualitative research focus group discussion the respondents answered that they felt in a state of bad mood especially when losing a game however it gives them fun.

In the summary of the qualitative research focus group discussion, most of the respondents answered that boredom and stress reliever are the factors that lead them to play online games. All of the respondents agreed that online games relieve their stresses from duty and exams also neither positive nor negative online gaming has affected their life. They mentioned that online gaming makes them experience eye pain and in a state of bad mood especially when losing a game but despite of experiencing those problems/consequences mentioned, they still play because it gives fun for them. The respondents mentioned that they can replace online gaming with many other things such as clubbing, sleeping, reading, drinking alcohol, washing clothes, hang out with friends and watching TV. In order for them to lessen their engagement with online games they would socialize with people. Most of the respondents answered that online games are addictive that they will not change or lessen playing online games unless they will experience the worst of the symptoms that they have experienced from playing online games.

Conclusions

Most of the students are now engaged with online gaming. Online gaming has both positive and negative effects to physical, mental and emotional health of the respondents either male or female gamers.

Majority of the gamers regarded online gaming as a stress reliever, uplift one's emotion though negative effects also occurs but its positive effects outweighs the negative ones.

There is no significant relationship between the amount of time spent on online gaming and health related effects of the students.

Recommendations

Grounded on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed :

1. Tailored Health Education Programs

Recognizing the demographic characteristics of the respondents, particularly the predominance of males , health education programs should be tailored to impart the effects of online gaming on students on their physical, mental and emotional health.

2. Educational and Counselling Programs

The students should be informed of the detrimental effects on the excessive online gaming and imparting preventative measures in the form of educational and counseling programs for students regarding the proper and practical use of the Internet in their education process and not excessively for online gaming.

3. Monitoring and Control

Monitoring and control be exercised on how the Internet is used by university students, and they should be informed of the detrimental effects of this technology in the case of misuse or overuse.

4. Address the issues and problems relating to communication technologies, such as the Internet, can lay the groundwork for proper education and instigate parents' and families' further attention to proper and effective use of the Internet on the education of the students.

5. Stress relief: Gaming can be a stress-relieving activity for students, helping them to unwind and relax after a long day.

6. Increased motivation: Achieving goals and progressing through levels in online games can be motivating for students, encouraging them to work hard and strive for success in other areas of their lives as well.

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